

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Role of *Viruddha Ahara* in allergic conditions W.S.R. *Veerya Viruddha*: An ayurvedic perspective

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Abstract

Viruddha Ahara i.e. unwholesome diet is a unique and important concept described in Ayurveda. *Viruddha Ahara* refers to food incompatibility including interaction between different types of food which disturb the homeostasis of body leading to various diseases specially skin disorders. In classical text description of different types of *Viruddha Ahara* is available like Samskara *Viruddha*, Samyoga *Viruddha*, *Veerya Viruddha* etc. In skin diseases, *Viruddha Ahara* is considered as one of the prime factor for causing the disease and amongst all the *Viruddha Ahara*, *Veerya Viruddha* is considered as the main cause. *Viruddha Ahara* have potential to triggers the pathogenesis of several diseases including *Visarpa*, intoxication, *Shukra Dhatu Dushti*, rhinitis, infertility, *Kustha roga* and allergic disorders, etc. this article explore the role of *Viruddha Ahara* in skin disorder.

Keywords: *Viruddha Ahara*; *Kustha Roga*; Incompatible Food; Skin disease

1. Introduction

Skin disorders are big challenge to the medical sciences since the time immemorial. The knowledge about skin and skin disorders are beautifully described in Ayurvedic literatures since *Vedic* period as *Kustha* is described as the *Samanya hetu* of *Nija Sotha*¹. It is also considered as *Sannipataja Vyadhi*². *Ahara*, *Nidra* and *Brahmacharya* are the three sub pillars which support the body itself³.

In present era, the era of modernization and industrialization everyone is busy in achieving their goals. Due to this hectic schedule no one have time to take proper food timely. Beside this, fast food also takes a big part in our life and these all comes under *Viruddha Ahara*. Consumption of *Viruddha Ahara* disturbs the homeostasis of body leading various diseases including the eight *Maharogas*, genetic disturbances and even sometimes leads to death. It is the common causative factor of skin disorder.

2. Material and methods

All the Ayurvedic texts were evaluated. The text from *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, *Ashtanga Hridaya*, *Ashtanga Sangraha* and their respective commentaries were thoroughly gone and online research papers from 2011 to 2021 viz. Pubmed, Google scholar and web of science by utilizing the words like daily regime, lifestyle disorders, *Ayurveda*, incompatible food, *Viruddha Ahara*, skin disorders, *Kushta* etc.

2.1. Definition of *Viruddha Ahara*

Viruddha Ahara is the combination of two or 3 substances, but not have affinity for each other⁴. The 18 types of *Viruddha Ahara* mentioned by Charak in *Sutrasthan* chapter 26 are⁵ *Desa Viruddha*, *Kala Viruddha*, *Agni Viruddha*, *Matra*

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Viruddha, Satmya Viruddha, Vata Viruddha, Samskara Viruddha, Virya Viruddha, Kostha Viruddha, Avastha Viruddha, Krama Viruddha, Parihara Viruddha, Upachara Viruddha, Paka Viruddha, Samyoga Viruddha, Hridaya Viruddha, Sampada Viruddha and Viddhi Viruddha. Acharya Sushruta has also mentioned 4 types of *Viruddha Ahara* as *Samyoga Viruddha, Karana Viruddha, Mana Viruddha (Matra Viruddha) and Rasa, Virya, Vipaka Viruddha*⁶.

2.2. Food intolerance in present era

Molecularly, *Viruddha Ahara* can cause inflammation in tissues. In order to understand modern food intolerances from an Ayurvedic perspective, we must identify new food incompatibilities. These dietary intolerances can also be divided into *Karma, Krama, Veerya*, and other types of *Viruddha*. Such meal combinations may have negative impacts on the immune system, cellular metabolism, growth hormone and Dehydroepiandrosterone Sulphate (DHEAS). A new field of study called topography, which studies the combination of food's fundamental categories, is beginning to take shape. According to this study, proteins can be ingested in numerous ways and shouldn't be consumed with starches and carbohydrates. This is because starches require an alkali medium and the amylase in saliva contains ptyalin, an enzyme that breaks down starch into maltose. More amylase is added to the process in the small intestine, where maltose is further broken down into simple glucose, fructose, and galactose. Inappropriate meal pairings can have negative effects on other physiological systems as well as the gastrointestinal tract. When two or more types of meals are ingested simultaneously, the body may experience the unintended side effects. Even while such reactions might not seem significant at the time, they might have catastrophic consequences if they lead to substantial side effects.

3. Discussion

3.1. On Veerya Viruddha

Veerya is the power or potency by which an action takes place. Nothing can be done in absence of *Veerya*. When *Dravyas* with opposite *Veerya* are used in combination is known as *Veerya Viruddha*. E.g. *Dravyas* with *Sheeta Veerya* are mixed with *Dravyas* with *Ushna Veerya* it results in *Veerya Viruddha*⁷.

Samyoga Viruddha is also known as *Veerya viruddha* and this condition is brought on by the combined actions of one or more of the elements, however it is not permanent. In another verse, Charak said that combining two or more substances is known as a combination⁸.

This combination has unique qualities that none of the individual components have ever possessed. For instance, the combination of milk and fish or honey and ghee has a poisonous effect that none of its components would have on its own. Although *Rasa- Veerya- Vipaka- Viruddha* is a distinct category, it can be grouped with *Samyoga Viruddha*, Acharya Sushruta has mentioned some examples like *Madhur + Amla, Madhur + Lavana Madhur + Katu, Amla + Tikta Amla+ Kasaya, Lavana + Kasaya Lavana+ Tikta, Katu+ Kasaya etc*⁹.

Although *Veerya Viruddha* and *Samyoga Viruddha* were categorized individually by Acharya Charak and Acharya Sushruta, but they are almost identical. The combination of foods that have the opposite *Veerya* is known as *Veerya Viruddha*. Here, Chakrapani uses the terms "*Veerya*" to refer to *Rasa, Veerya*, and *Vipaka*. Therefore, *Samyoga Viruddha* can be included in *Veerya Viruddha*.

3.2. On Disease review

Kotha, Utkotha, and Shitapitta are examples of Kustha Roga, which are classified as allergic skin illnesses. Shitapita is typically not mentioned in Brihatrayee, but Udarda, Kotha, and Utkotha are explained in Brihatrayee as Vyadhi, Purvarupa, or Lakshana. According to Ayurveda, exposure to Asatmya Ahara-Vihara (*Viruddha*) and interaction with many harmful food items (allergens) cause allergic manifestations.

3.2.1. Nidan

Viruddha Ahara and Rakta Dushti are causative factors in skin diseases¹⁰.

3.2.2. Etiopathogenesis

Nidan sevan → Tridosha Prakopa → mixes with Pitta → Dosha Dushya Sammurchana → Srotodushti → Bahir anatah visarpatah → Sheetapitta udarda, Kotha utkotha.

3.2.3. Samprapti ghatak

- Dosh: Tridosha
- Agni: Manda
- Doshagati: Vriddhi, tiryak, Shakha
- Vyadhimarga: Bahya
- Dushya: Rasa, Rakta Srotas: Rsavaha, Ratavaha
- Srotodushti: Viamarga Gaman
- Swabhava: Ashukari

Therefore, these skin conditions can be categorised as type 1- hypersensitivity, or acute hypersensitivity. Within minutes of the interaction of an antigen with an antibody attached to mast cells, it induces immunologic response. The IgE-mediated type of hypersensitivity is type 1. Immediate hypersensitivity can occur as a systemic disorder or as a local reaction. Localized cutaneous swelling (skin allergy), nasal and conjunctival discharge, allergic bronchial asthma, and allergic gastroenteritis are just a few examples of the several types of local reactions that might occur based on the allergen's entry point. Urticaria and the aforementioned skin disorders are both brought on by contact to the same allergens. Hypersensitivity type 1 mediated is also the case. Foods (such as nuts, eggs, fresh fruits, seafood, milk, and cheese), medications (such as pain relievers and antibiotics) as well as insects (such as bee stings and contact ants) are examples of IgE antibody-mediated causes of urticaria.

3.2.4. Etiopathogenesis (correlation between Ayurveda and contemporary science)

When skin comes in contact with allergens (*Sanchaya*), it leads to Production of primary T lymphocytes occurs to induce cell mediated immune response (*Prakopa*) and Join the recirculation pool i.e. in blood, lymphnodes etc. (*Prasara*) which leads to the Migration of these cells in subsequent antigenic challenge from blood to tissue (*Sthana Samshraya*) where T lymphocytes binds to the antigen by surface receptors and release lymphokine cause Itching, vesiculation, redness (*Vyakti*).if this condition occurs repeatedly it leads to Chronicity (*Bheda Avastha*).

4. Conclusion

From the above discussion, it can be conclude that *Kustha* is one of the major illnesses brought on by consumption *Viruddha Ahara*. *Viruddha Ahara* is a significant component of the unhealthful eating practices. Regular consumption of *Viruddha Ahara* acts as a poison and aggravates all of the *Doshas*. Hence, avoidance of intake of *Viruddha Ahara* plays a key role in prevention of diseases.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

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